

5. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **59**, 212.
6. W. J. EILBECK, F. HOLMS and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1967, 759.
7. W. J. DAVIS and J. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1974, 317.
8. K. J. REEDIS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1969, **3**, 617.
9. C. D. BURBRIDGE and D. M. L. GOODGAME, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1979, **4**, 231.
10. A. K. DAS and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 480.
11. J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. FUJITA, S. FRAZ, D. T. PHILLIPS and S. Y. TYREE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3770.
12. W. ROY MASON and H. B. GRAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5221.
13. H. B. GRAY and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
14. J. SCHERZER, P. PHILLIPS, L. OLAPP and J. EDWARDS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 847.
15. H. H. SCHMIDTKE, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1965, **339**, 103.
16. A. W. ADDISON, K. DAWSON, R. D. GILLARD, B. T. HEATON and H. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 589.
17. N. S. GILL, R. H. NATTALL, D. E. SCAIFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 79.
18. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1967, pp. 167, 173.
19. B. M. GATHOUSE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 79.
20. J. L. BURMIESTER and F. BASOLO, *Inorg. Chem.* 1964, **3**, 1587.

Synthesis and Characterisation of Lanthanide(III) Perrhenate Adducts of *N,N'*-Dioxides of 1,10-Phenanthroline and 2,2'-Bipyridine

R. K. AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, Lajpat Rai (Post-Graduate) College, Sahibabad-201 005

Manuscript received 13 November 1986, revised 29 June 1987, accepted 10 July 1987

THE synthesis of lanthanide(III) perrhenate adducts with 1,10-phenanthroline *N,N'*-dioxide (PhenNO₂) and 2,2'-bipyridine *N,N'*-dioxide (BipyNO₂) is reported in this communication.

Experimental

The hydrated lanthanide(III) perrhenates were obtained by reaction of dilute perrhenic acid and lanthanide basic carbonate¹. The ligands PhenNO₂ and BipyNO₂ were prepared from 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridine, respectively, as reported earlier^{2,3}. All the adducts were isolated by the following general method. Lanthanide(III) perrhenate (1 mmol) was dissolved in a mixture of ethanol (10 ml) and 2,2'-dimethoxypropane (5 ml) and refluxed for 15 min. The mixture was treated with a solution of the ligand (2.25 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml). The complexes separated on cooling were washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses, conductance and magnetic susceptibilities of the newly synthesised complexes were determined as before^{4,5}. All the complexes have the general composition Ln(ReO₄)₃.2L (Ln = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho or Yb; L = PhenNO₂ or BipyNO₂). The complexes were slightly hygroscopic. The molar conductivity values in nitromethane in the range 91.6–98.9 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ suggest that they behave as 1 : 1 electrolyte⁶. The magnetic moment values of lanthanide(III) complexes (Table 1) show a slight deviation from the Van Vleck values^{7,8}, thereby indicating that 4f-electrons do not take part in bond formation in these compounds.

The ir spectra of all the complexes were similar showing no significant dependence on the central metal ion. In free ligand, ν_{N-O} at 1 312 and 1 282 cm⁻¹ (in the case of PhenNO₂)^{9,10} and 1 264 and 1 260 cm⁻¹ (for BipyNO₂)¹¹ shifted to lower frequencies upon complex formation indicating O,O-chelation by PhenNO₂ and BipyNO₂ in these complexes¹². Slight shift of the NO bending band (855–840 cm⁻¹) provides further supports oxygen linkage between metal and the ligands. In the far-ir region (410–385 cm⁻¹), metal–ligand vibrations have been identified.

The complexes behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes, thus it may be suggestive that the complexes contain ionic as well as covalent ReO₄⁻ ions. The strong band (ν₈) at ~900 cm⁻¹ observed for perrhenate indicate that T_d symmetry of this ion is maintained and it is not coordinated to the tripositive lantha-

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC MOMENT (μ_{eff}, B.M.) VALUES OF COMPLEXES AT 303 K

Ln	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Yb
Ln(ReO ₄) ₃ .2PhenNO ₂	Diamag	2.54	3.60	3.58	1.61	7.90	9.90	10.47	10.48	4.25
Ln(ReO ₄) ₃ .2BipyNO ₂	Diamag.	2.56	3.64	3.56	1.59	7.91	9.29	10.45	10.47	4.26

anides. The other bands attribute to bidentate perrhenates^{1,18-15}.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support and to Dr. G. D. Sharma, Principal, Lajpat Rai (Post-Graduate) College, Sahibabad, for taking keen interest in the work.

References

1. G. VICENTINI, M. PERRIER and J. C. PRADO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 825.
2. G. M. BADGER and W. H. F. SASSE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 617.
3. P. G. SIMPSON, A. VINCIGUERRA and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 282.
4. R. K. AGARWAL and S. K. GUPTA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1986, **98**, 313; 1986, **99**, 357.
5. R. K. AGARWAL and S. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 597.
6. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
7. D. M. YOST, H. RUSSEL and C. S. GARNER, "The Rare Earth Elements and their Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1947.
8. J. H. VAN VLICK and A. FRANK, *Phys. Rev.*, 1929, **34**, 1494.
9. B. E. BRIDGLAND and W. R. MCGREGOR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **43**, 31.
10. C. CHASSAFIS and G. PNEUMATIKAKIS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, **27**, 67.
11. S. K. MADAN and A. M. DONOHUE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1303.
12. N. M. KARAYANNIS, A. N. SPECA, D. E. CHASAN and L. L. PYTLEWSKI, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1976, **20**, 37.
13. G. VICENTINI, M. PERRIER and J. C. PRADO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 825.
14. G. VICENTINI and D. J. S. NUNES, *An. Acad. Bras. Cienc.*, 1974, **5**, 46.
15. V. V. KRAVCHENKO and K. I. PETROV, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1974, **19**, 186.

Synthesis of Indenyl and Fluorenyl Compounds of some Lanthanides

R. K. SHARMA and C. P. SHARMA*

National Physical Laboratory, Hillside Road,
New Delhi-110 012

Manuscript received 7 April 1986, revised 9 June 1987,
accepted 6 July 1987

THE only reported organolanthanide derivatives contain the cyclopentadienyl¹, indenyl^{2,3}, cyclooctatetraenyl⁴, and phenyl groups aside from the divalent compounds, Eu(C₈H₈)₂, Yb(C₈H₈)₂, Sm(C₈H₈)₂, OC₄H₈(1) and Ln(C₈H₈)₃, where Ln = Eu, Yb⁴, all these compounds involve the +3 oxidation state of the lanthanides. Although some attempts have been made to prepare alkyl and aryl derivatives⁵⁻⁷, no well characterised compound of this type have been prepared. Biphenyl was the only product isolated from both the sealed tube reaction of diphenyl mercury with metallic lanthanum at 135° for 100 h followed by treatment with carbon dioxide and of lanthanum trichloride with phenyl lithium in diethyl ether⁸. The present communication describes the preparation and

characterisation of triindenyl complexes of Sc, Y, Ce, Pr and Nd and trifluorenyl complexes of Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Gd, Dy and Sm in +3 oxidation state.

Experimental

All operations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Tetrahydrofuran was purified by distillation over Na and then over lithium hydride.

Potassium fluorenyl and indenyl: Potassium fluorenyl and potassium indenyl were prepared by treating potassium metal (1.17 g, 0.03 mol) with fluorene (5 g, 0.03 mol) and indene (3.5 g, 0.03 mol), respectively, in tetrahydrofuran with refluxing and stirring. Potassium reacted completely with indene to give dark brown coloured potassium indenyl in 2 h, whereas with fluorene it gave an orange coloured solution of potassium fluorenyl in 2.5 h.

Triindenyl lanthanides derivatives: Triindenyl complexes of Sc, Y, Ce, Pr and Nd were prepared by treating the corresponding anhydrous trichloride (1 mol) with potassium indenyl (3 mol) in tetrahydrofuran. The reaction mixture was stirred for 8 h at room temperature followed by gentle reflux for 1-2 h to ensure complete reaction. The reaction mixture was filtered through G-4 sintered glass disc. Bulk of THF was distilled off under reduced pressure and the compounds were precipitated by adding petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). The precipitate was filtered through a G-4 sintered glass frit and dried under reduced pressure.

Microanalytical data of these complexes are given in Table I.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF TRIINDENYL AND TRIFLUORENYL COMPLEXES OF LANTHANIDES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		C	H	Lanth.
(C ₉ H ₇) ₃ Sc	Scarlet	82.72 (83.08)	5.04 (5.99)	10.90 (11.53)
(C ₉ H ₇) ₃ Y	Light brown	74.13 (74.67)	4.52 (4.84)	19.80 (20.49)
(C ₉ H ₇) ₃ Ce	Violet	65.90 (66.79)	3.87 (4.33)	28.00 (28.88)
(C ₉ H ₇) ₃ Pr	Yellow	66.00 (66.68)	3.90 (4.32)	28.16 (29.00)
(C ₉ H ₇) ₃ Nd	Dark brown	65.18 (66.23)	3.88 (4.30)	28.82 (29.47)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ Sc	Brown	85.80 (86.67)	4.80 (5.0)	7.52 (8.33)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ Y	Colourless	79.42 (80.15)	4.31 (4.62)	14.01 (15.28)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ La	Light yellow	73.02 (73.83)	4.00 (4.26)	20.80 (21.91)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ Ce	Pale yellow	73.11 (73.69)	3.96 (4.25)	21.50 (22.06)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ Pr	Green	72.94 (73.59)	3.98 (4.25)	21.48 (22.16)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ Nd	Yellow	72.04 (73.21)	3.90 (4.22)	21.90 (22.57)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ Gd	Colourless	71.20 (71.75)	3.74 (4.14)	22.87 (24.11)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ Dy	Colourless	70.69 (71.18)	3.76 (4.10)	23.30 (24.72)
(C ₁₁ H ₉) ₃ Sm	Yellow	71.90 (72.52)	3.90 (4.18)	22.00 (22.90)